

DELIVERABLE D3.2

ELIGIBILITY FOR “EATRIS CERTIFICATE OF COMMITMENT TO QUALITY”

WP3 – Quality Assessment for Omics Technologies

Lead Beneficiary: University of Helsinki (UH)

WP Leader and Institution: Andreas Scherer (UH)

Contributing Partner(s): EATRIS, UP, SERMAS, UU, IBBL, RUMC, UU

Contractual Delivery Date: 31/08/2021 (M20)

Actual Delivery Date: 12/11/2021

Authors of Deliverable: Andreas Scherer (UH)

Grant agreement no. 871096

Horizon 2020

H2020-INFRADEV-3

Type of Action: RIA

Contents

Executive summary	3
Project objectives.....	3
Detailed report on the deliverable	3
Background	3
Description of work.....	4
Next steps	8
Abbreviations.....	8
Delivery and schedule.....	8
Adjustments made.....	9
Appendices.....	10

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The EATRIS-Plus project emphasizes the importance of research quality and scientific rigor. This deliverable establishes criteria for awarding *EATRIS Certificate of Commitment to Quality (ECCQ)*, and the process of issuing the award. The criteria will also play an important role for the process of applying for membership to the EATRIS ERIC infrastructure, as they will provide additional ways of evaluating the commitment to quality of the applicant. As users of the infrastructure are more likely to select EATRIS sites with demonstrated efforts in the field of quality assurance, an incentive for application is increased project provision and thereby financial benefit.

PROJECT OBJECTIVES

To highlight the commitment of EATRIS institutions to quality standards and guidelines and thereby increase trust of the users, EATRIS-Plus participants will define, pilot and disseminate the “EATRIS Certificate of Commitment to Quality”. EATRIS institutions will apply for the ECCQ by providing evidence not only of their commitment to quality assurance in certain key technology areas, but also to training and education, and other means to assure scientific rigor. Examples of such commitment include, but are not limited to, the active participation in EATRIS’ quality initiatives or other internationally recognised quality assessment programmes, adherence to site-internal quality review processes, or positive evaluation in ring-testing, and further documentation of the site’s focus on scientific quality. The EATRIS-Plus Steering Committee will review the applications and make a recommendation to the EATRIS Board of National Directors (BoND) either to award the ECCQ or to reject the application. The applicants will receive feedback so that they may address the identified limitations, and reapply, or they will be rewarded with the certificate.

The task will:

- Develop measures of credentials towards eligibility for ECCQ. Measures will include documentation on commitment to quality research, such as the questionnaire;
- Develop a process for identifying and awarding eligible sites;
- Award the ECCQ to EATRIS institutions committed to quality;
- Increase visibility of certified sites and support communication of quality services to users.

DETAILED REPORT ON THE DELIVERABLE

BACKGROUND

Scientific rigor is based on the mindset which strives for quality and experimental excellence. Many factors influence the level of quality produced in a laboratory: transparency, documentation, traceability of data, storage of data and material, training, and consideration and implementation of best practice principles. Within EATRIS-Plus, re-usability of the multiomics data is an essential

component of success, and it is based on data quality. It is therefore essential that EATRIS-Plus participants work according to the FAIR principles (findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable), and are able to document these. In addition, the EATRIS leadership requires criteria by which it can assess the commitment of EATRIS member sites and membership applicants to scientific rigor. An award which certifies such a commitment will strengthen the role and visibility not only of the awardees, but also of EATRIS as an organisation which demands scientific quality in order to meet its mission of helping move scientific findings down the drug development trajectory. Facilities with such an award will certainly be preferred by external users of the infrastructure, and is foreseen to promote a site in funding applications and external communication.

The assessment process developed in this deliverable will provide EATRIS leadership with degrees of confidence in the level of commitment to scientific quality. It will and cannot though replace certification or accreditation programmes by other organisations, such as EQIPD or ISO.

DESCRIPTION OF WORK

The following principles of the “EATRIS Certificate of Commitment to Quality” (ECCQ) were developed with consultation of EQIPD (<https://quality-preclinical-data.eu/>), the IMI-project for European Quality in Preclinical Data. Both parties agreed that it was in both EATRIS’ and EQIPD’s interest to create a system which clearly keeps EATRIS’ award and EQIPD certification programme separate and identifiable by users. However, both organisations are very interested in strengthening existing ties and collaborations in the future, e.g. by advocating for EQIPD’s certification process.

NATURE OF AWARD

The EATRIS Certificate of Commitment to Quality (ECCQ) process is inclusive and designed to support those who do not comply yet with all requirements in trying to achieve the goals and strive for better scientific conduct, or simply fail to provide sufficient supporting evidence.

WHO WILL BE AWARDED?

The certificate may be applied for by existing members of EATRIS. In addition, it will be an integral part of the application process for new membership.

The certificate will be awarded to organisations who provide documentation of their commitment to scientific rigor. The questionnaire will provide suggestions for such documents, but any other evidence may be provided. Only laboratories or core facilities will be considered for the award. Awarding the Certificate to entire Departments, Universities or Hospitals may not result in a clear picture of the research quality situation but by nature must stay superficial, and not reflect the actual situation in each laboratory. Therefore, any feedback from EATRIS will have to remain superficial as well and may

not be very instructive or helpful towards any improvement. Also, should a Certificate be awarded to an upper-level unit, it may go unknown to the individual laboratories. The provided information in the application should be focused on the laboratory or core facility and thereby easier to assess. Having been awarded the EATRIS Certificate of Commitment to Quality may be an incentive to other laboratories to follow the same procedure. Individual research groups and core-facilities are invited to apply. Receiving the award is incentivized by the probability, that facilities with the ECCQ may also be preferred by external users of the infrastructure when selecting service providers or consortium partners.

Therefore, individual EATRIS research groups or core facilities are eligible to apply, either based on their research area, or by their services.

Research facilities applying to become EATRIS service providers as part of their member institution should acknowledge that they are committed to adhere to the principles of good scientific conduct and must apply for the certificate for the services as part of the application process. An initial negative decision on the ECCQ application does not necessarily exclude the facility from joining EATRIS, if other evidence of its excellence can be provided. The evaluation by EATRIS will be constructive and is aimed at improving the response to the questionnaire and the overall performance in the application process. In a possibly rare event of a negative decision EATRIS will offer of work closely with and in support of the applicant to find a way of addressing the issues, such that a positive evaluation can be made in a future re-application.

Criteria in favor of a positive decision are the provision of answers and documentation showing the commitment to quality service or research. Where answers can not be given in a satisfactory manner, an interview-like discussion may solve potential issues. In case, such an interview is not satisfactory to EATRIS, the applicant is invited to re-apply after a time period which seems sufficient for addressing and/or solving the outstanding issues. If EATRIS agrees, this process does not necessarily infringe a membership application process. However, the goal should be that new members receive the ECCQ within the first year of their membership, and that EATRIS and the applicant work towards that goal.

PROCESS

As part of the evaluation process, the EATRIS team will take several criteria into consideration. Criteria for a positive evaluation are:

1. Self-assessment by the applicant (completion of the questionnaire and providing supporting documentation)
2. Interview (by a group of 3 to 5 EATRIS representatives)
3. participation in comparative technology studies, other practical participation in quality-oriented groups
4. Existing accreditation or certification

The applicant will be invited to fill in the questionnaire, providing supporting documentation of the claims they make. The material will then be evaluated by a group of EATRIS representatives, e.g. the

EATRIS-Plus Steering Committee. After initial evaluation, the applicant will be invited to an online or on-site interview where further supporting information may be provided and open questions can be discussed.

In case applicants are already certified or accredited, the evaluation process will be simplified.

Following the interview, the evaluation team will conclude on the application. In the given absence of a qualitative system, the decision will have to be made on grounds of subjectivity of demonstrable reason. In the case of a positive decision, a Certificate will be signed by the EATRIS Chair of the Board of National Directors as well as the EATRIS Scientific Director, and provided to the applicant.

The evaluation by EATRIS will be constructive and is aimed at improving the response to the questionnaire and the overall performance in the application process.

Criteria in favor of a positive decision are the provision of answers and documentation in the questionnaire, showing the commitment to quality service or research. This step will be followed by an interview, where answers will be discussed in a constructive manner, in which suggestions for improvement of the situation can be made by both parties. In case, such an interview is not satisfactory to EATRIS, the applicant is invited to re-apply after a time period which seems sufficient for addressing and/or solving the outstanding issues. EATRIS agrees that this process does not necessarily infringe a membership application process. However, the goal should be that new members receive the ECCQ within the first year of their membership, and that EATRIS and the applicant work towards that goal.

In addition, EATRIS may decide to implement assessment of methodological quality in a laboratory. The extent and nature of such assessments is subject of further discussions.

The entire review process should not take longer than 3 months, depending on the availability of the participants.

A ECCQ may be valid for two years, after which the facility representative is invited for an interview in which the current situation and any changes from the previous interview will be discussed. There should be no need to fill in the questionnaire again. This scenario can be repeated several times.

The process is outlined in Figure 1.

Figure 1.

Workflow of the evaluation of existing members ("Lab A" on the left) and new applicants of EATRIS membership (Lab B, on the right).

Figure 2

Design of the EATRIS Certificate of Commitment to Quality

NEXT STEPS

In a pilot phase, EATRIS-Plus participants will be notified of the possibility to apply for the ECCQ, and first assessments will be conducted.

ABBREVIATIONS

IBBL, Integrated BioBank of Luxembourg

RUMC, Radboud University Medical Centre,

SERMAS, Servicio Madrilenio de Salud

SOP, Standard Operating Procedure

UH, University of Helsinki

UP, Univerzita Palacky v Olomouci

UU, University of Uppsala

DELIVERY AND SCHEDULE

A 3-month extension to the deliverable was applied for on 08/06/21 and granted on 15/06/21. Initial due date of the deliverable was foreseen on 31/08/21. The actual delivery date is 12/11/21.

ADJUSTMENTS MADE

n/a

APPENDICES

Appendix 1 - EATRIS Certificate of Commitment to Quality Self Assessment Questionnaire for applicants

Appendix 1 - EATRIS Certificate of Commitment to Quality - Self Assessment Questionnaire

QUESTION Category	#	QUESTION	Comment	ANSWER	
General Organisation, Management and Governance		General Organisation, Management and Governance: Description in your own words. Please provide supporting documentation where possible.		free text	
	1	Quality Assurance / Management Is there a dedicated quality management role (internal or external)?		please select	
		If yes, please list the responsibilities of this quality function:...		free text	
		If no or n/a, how is quality managed?: ...		free text	
	2	Accreditations and certifications Does the organization/laboratory work under accreditation/certification?		please select	
		If yes, please indicate which Quality System is adhered to:		free text	
		If yes, please add copy of certificate including related scope (list of assays/techniques)		free text	
	3	Does your facility work with animals, ionising radiation, controlled substances, biohazardous materials, genetically modified organisms or other experimental systems whose use is regulated?		please select	
		If yes, please specify ...		free text	
		If yes, does your facility have the required licences for this type of work?		please select	
4	Research Quality Does your facility work under a Quality Management System for non-GLP research?		please select		
	- EQIPD		please select		
	- WHO		please select		
	- RQA		please select		
	- Joint Code of Practice		please select		
	- internally developed system (please provide details)		free text		
5	Personnel and Training Do you have a training curriculum to ensure your research staff are appropriately trained to be able to conduct their individual tasks properly?		please select		
	6	What is documented in terms of training?		please select	
Facility and Equipment		Facility and Equipment: please describe your current situation and plans in your own words. Please provide supporting documentation where possible.		free text	
	7	Access Is access restricted to your facility and/or laboratory at the level of:		please select	
		the organisation		please select	
		the building		please select	
		the facility		please select	
	8	Secure long term data storage For what type of data do you ensure long term storage?		please select	storage location: timing of storage: storage duration: free text (if needed)
		- experimental procedure/protocol		please select	storage location: timing of storage: storage duration: free text (if needed)
		- raw data (first numeric data)		please select	storage location: timing of storage: storage duration: free text (if needed)
		- processed (analysed) data		please select	storage location: timing of storage: storage duration: free text (if needed)
		- notebook records		please select	storage location: timing of storage: storage duration: free text (if needed)
- interim or final reports			please select	storage location: timing of storage: storage duration: free text (if needed)	
- training records			please select	storage location: timing of storage: storage duration: free text (if needed)	
- equipment maintenance/calibration			please select	storage location: timing of storage: storage duration: free text (if needed)	
- other (please specify)		free text	storage location: timing of storage: storage duration: free text (if needed)		
9	Do your long term storage solution(s) have the following attributes:		please select	If yes, can the audit trail be modified?	
	- is there access control?		please select		
	- is there regular and permanent backup?		please select		
	- are data stored in an un-editable format?		please select		
10	Storage of samples, reagents and materials Are environmental and temperature sensitive storage equipment locations in the laboratory controlled, alarmed and monitored?		please select		
	If no, please provide details why this is not needed or not done		free text		

	11	Equipment Is key equipment <i>routinely</i> maintained and calibrated to ensure it remains functioning and fit for purpose? If yes, both maintenance and calibration activities documented?	<i>please select</i>	
	12	Computerized systems Are computerized systems used in support of studies? <i>If no, please skip questions 13-16</i>	<i>please select</i>	<i>free text - please add comments if necessary</i>
	13	Have you verified that computerized systems ensure outcomes are reliable, accurate (e.g. correctness of calculations) and secure (e.g. protected against loss)? If not, what controls are used (e.g. QC checks on data transfers)?	<i>please select</i>	
	14	Are your computerized systems access restricted?	<i>please select</i>	
	15	Do your computerized systems have an audit trail to track changes to experimental data including the following: username, date, time, new data value, old data value, and reason for change (if available)? If yes, is the audit trail protected against modification?	<i>please select</i>	
	16	Are documented processes in place to ensure data recovery and business continuity in case of issue (at the level of the facility, personnel or equipment)? If yes, have they been tested?	<i>please select</i>	
Research Materials, Reagents and Samples		Research Materials, Reagents and Samples: please describe processes (in place or planned) receiving, handling, labelling, tracking, storing, shipping and disposing key samples, materials and reagents in your	free text	
	17	Is there a process in place for receiving, handling, labelling, tracking, storing, shipping and disposing key samples, materials and reagents? If yes, is this process documented? If yes, for what types of samples and materials?	<i>please select</i> <i>please select</i> <i>free text</i>	
Experimental design (risks of bias)		Experimental design (risks of bias): please describe experimental design strategies (in place or planned) in your own words. Please provide documentation.	free text	
	18	Is randomization applied to allocate experimental units to control and treatment groups?	<i>please select</i>	
	19	Are curve fitting rules established prior to data collection for in vitro tests?	<i>please select</i>	
	20	Is blinding applied? - during treatment group allocation - during conduct of the experiment - during data analysis	<i>please select</i> <i>please select</i> <i>please select</i>	
	21	Are biostatisticians consulted: - for experimental design planning? - for data analysis?	<i>please select</i> <i>please select</i>	
	22	Is power calculation performed to estimate sample size?	<i>please select</i>	
Process and Methods		Process and Methods: please describe process management (planned or in place) in your own words. Please provide supporting documentation where possible.	free text	
	23	Process management and documentation: Are there written descriptions of routine experimental methods and processes such as SOPs, procedures or work instructions?	<i>please select</i>	
	24	Protocol / Process / Method documentation Is a study plan/protocol usually available prior to study conduct?	<i>please select</i>	
	25	Does the study plan/protocol include all details (or references) to enable full reconstruction of the activity such as:		
		- unique study identifier enabling linkage with study data and reports	<i>please select</i>	
		- objective	<i>please select</i>	
		- test methods/procedures	<i>please select</i>	
		- materials and equipment	<i>please select</i>	
- key reagents and kits		<i>please select</i>		
- test article including reference compounds, controls	<i>please select</i>			
- test system such as cell line, animal species, ...	<i>please select</i>			
- statistical tools	<i>please select</i>			
- acceptance ranges to validate/invalidate experiments for reference items, control samples or standard curves	<i>please select</i>			

		- criteria for excluding data points (e.g. outliers)	<i>please select</i>
Experimental documentation, research records, report and research reconstruction / retrieval		Experimental documentation, research records, report and research reconstruction / retrieval: please describe methods of documentation (in place or planned) in your own words. Please provide supporting documentation where possible.	free text
	26	Please specify which experimental/analytical details are contained in experimental records:	
		- name of scientist(s) involved	<i>please select</i>
		- study plan/protocol	<i>please select</i>
		- procedures/test methods	<i>please select</i>
		- statistical tools/methods	<i>please select</i>
		- materials and equipment	<i>please select</i>
		- key reagents and kits	<i>please select</i>
		- test article including reference compounds, controls	<i>please select</i>
		- test system such as cell line, animal species, ...	<i>please select</i>
		- computerized systems	<i>please select</i>
		- dates each activity was performed	<i>please select</i>
		- raw data (first numeric data) and its location	<i>please select</i>
		- processed (analyzed) data	<i>please select</i>
- results interpretations and conclusion	<i>please select</i>		
- any other details required for reconstruction	free text		
27	When do you document experimental / analytical details? If other, please provide more details:	<i>please select</i> free text	
28	Are amendments (planned changes) and deviations (unplanned changes) to experimental procedures documented? If yes, please specify how:	<i>please select</i> <i>please select</i>	
29	Are critical incidents and errors during study conduct and their resolution documented? If yes, where:	<i>please select</i> <i>please select</i>	
30	Do you have a procedure in place to notify sponsors / collaborators about study plan amendments, deviations, potentially impactful incidents and/or errors during study conduct? If yes, when:	<i>please select</i> <i>please select</i>	
31	Are reasons for exclusion of data recorded and reported?	<i>please select</i>	
32	Do reported data disclose all repetitions of the test/study regardless of the outcome?	<i>please select</i>	
33	If there are study limitations (e.g. in design, robustness of assays or conduct of the experiment), are these routinely mentioned in the study report?	<i>please select</i>	
Record review		Record Review: Please describe methods for record review (in place or planned) in your own words. Please provide supporting documentation where possible.	free text
	34	Is there a review for completeness and accuracy by another person? If yes, at what level:	<i>please select</i>
		- at level of raw data	<i>please select</i>
		- at level of processed data	<i>please select</i>
	35	- at level of interim or final reports	<i>please select</i>
		If you use a lab notebook, are experiment records signed and dated by responsible researcher? If "yes", please provide timeline within which this needs to be performed?	<i>please select</i> free text
36	If you use a lab notebook, are experiment records signed and dated by another person (read and understood)? If "yes", please provide timeline within which this needs to be performed after entering data in the lab notebook?	<i>please select</i> free text	
	37	Are there regular checks performed (by peers, manager, quality professional):	
- on accurate data recording?		<i>please select</i>	
- on the secure storage of data?		<i>please select</i>	
- on the ability to trace reported data from the experimental data?		<i>please select</i>	
		- on the reliability of data (e.g. errors during data processing and reporting)?	<i>please select</i>
Outsourcing		Outsourcing: please describe the outsourcing activities (in place or planned) in your own words. Please provide supporting documentation where possible.	free text
	38	Does your lab utilize subcontractors for any of the services you provide?	
	39	If yes, do you have a process to ensure outsourced activities are performed in compliance with your quality requirements, Good Research Practice and data integrity principles?	<i>please select</i>
		Publishing: please describe the publishing strategy in your own words	

Publishing	40	Does lab publish under an Open Access license?	<i>please select</i>
	41	Do you post preprints of your research articles before peer review or publication?	<i>please select</i>
	42	Do you deposit your published articles in an institutional or other repository?	<i>please select</i>
	43	Do you share your raw data?	<i>please select</i>
	44	Do you publish peer reviews alongside your research articles?	<i>please select</i>
	45	Do you share detailed methods information beyond what is typical for the methods section of a manuscript (for example materials and reagents, protocols, code and custom software, or full methods articles)?	<i>please select</i>
	46	Do you preregister confirmatory research by depositing your study design with a repository or publishing it in a journal?	<i>please select</i>
	47	Do you comment on posted preprints and published research articles?	<i>please select</i>
	48	Do you sign your own peer reviews?	<i>please select</i>
	49	Do you support others in their own Open Science practices?	<i>please select</i>